

Exploring Probabilistic Data Structures for Multipath Route Optimization in Named Data Networks

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Abstract—Routing protocols are crucial for reachability discovery in Named Data Networking (NDN). Link State-based protocols, like NLSR, are less suitable for networks with multiple paths due to high synchronization complexity and computational demands. Distance Vector-based protocols, while less complex, struggle in multipath scenarios. We propose the use of probabilistic data structures in distance vector protocols to address these challenges. Our results show that this approach enhances the NDN packet delivery rate and significantly reduces unsatisfied interests. Future works will focus on refining the proposal to integrate it with forwarding strategies, leveraging the benefits for optimized routes.

Index Terms—Network routing, Protocol, Multipath, Distance Vector, Probability, Data structures.

I. INTRODUCTION

NAMED Data Networking (NDN) has emerged as a promising Internet architecture, enhancing the performance and security of legacy TCP/IP networks. It introduces native features for secure and efficient data delivery, such as in-network caching, per-packet encryption, and packet aggregation. In this paradigm, communication follows a data-driven model in which nodes act as consumers – requesting specific data – or producers – providing it on demand [1].

Routing protocols are essential in NDN, as they establish paths to name prefixes, enabling data retrieval [2]. These protocols are generally classified as: (i) Link State (LS), which requires a global view of the network; and (ii) Distance Vector (DV), which computes routes using local, decentralized information.

Despite their effectiveness, both categories face challenges when handling multiple path scenarios. While LS protocols use Dijkstra’s algorithm to compute optimal routes, their reliance on global knowledge increases computational overhead and limits scalability. DV protocols, based on the Bellman-Ford algorithm, are more scalable but are prone to routing loops and cannot ensure disjoint paths, affecting performance in multipath scenarios.

To address these limitations, we propose PathVector, a Distance Vector routing protocol for NDN that supports multiple and potentially non-disjoint paths. It uses probabilistic data structures to disseminate routing information and identify efficient paths. A probabilistic filter discards suboptimal routes with minimal overhead, maintaining both scalability and performance.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews the theoretical background and related work. Section III presents the problem and the proposed solution, highlighting the benefits of probabilistic structures in route discovery. Section IV details the experimental setup and results. Section V concludes the paper and outlines future work.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Multipath Routing in NDN

Over the years, several routing protocols have been proposed for NDN. One of the first was the Named-data Link State Routing protocol (NLSR), which uses a link-state approach. However, NLSR faces scalability issues due to the overhead of each node independently building a full view of the network topology, a limitation that becomes more pronounced in multipath scenarios.

To address multipath routing, adaptations of the Dijkstra algorithm have been explored. Although the core mechanism still computes the shortest paths from a node to all others, it is modified to probe multiple routes. The algorithm evaluates each neighbor and interface separately, calculating costs to all reachable prefixes. After collecting this data, it ranks the best paths. Despite this, the approach assumes global topology knowledge, requiring complex synchronization and incurring in significant overhead. Additionally, as Dijkstra was originally designed to find a single optimal path, it may fail to deliver high-quality alternatives in multipath settings [2].

Another approach is the Multipath Forwarding and In-network Caching protocol (MUCA), which combines link-state and distance-vector strategies and can incorporate routes from the Content Store (CS) [3]. While MUCA’s hybrid design has advantages, it still inherits limitations from link-state protocols. In contrast, the Bloom Filter-based Routing protocol (BFR) [4] uses probabilistic data structures to determine prefix reachability via next hops. Although a pull-based BFR variant was developed to enhance scalability, it did not improve route quality in multipath contexts.

Finally, the NDN Distance Vector Routing protocol (NDVR) [5] is an asynchronous, lightweight, and secure DV-based protocol that supports multipath routing by advertising multiple paths to reachable prefixes. However, its use of the Bellman-Ford algorithm (BFA) limits route quality in networks with loops or non-disjoint paths, often leading to inefficient forwarding and bottlenecks. This work proposes solutions to mitigate these issues, as detailed in the following sections.

B. Probabilistic data structures

Probabilistic data structures enable the storage of large amounts of data using minimal space, at the cost of a small

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(a) Bottleneck in node F (packets coming from node E and C are forwarded through the same exit link).

(b) Available paths for packets originating from node C to node D .

Figure 1. Illustration of multipath problems in looped networks.

error rate. In 1970, Burton Bloom introduced two foundational approaches for such structures [6]. The first, called “hashing with partial codes and allowed errors”, uses cells similar to traditional methods but stores only part of the message to save space, introducing a small error margin. The second method maps each message to a hash and sets bits at specific positions in an array, further reducing space usage while allowing false positives. Our solution builds on this second method, as detailed in the following sections.

III. PATH OPTIMIZATION WITH PROBABILISTIC DATA STRUCTURES

Distance vector protocols advertise least-cost paths [7], which can result in non-disjoint or looped routes in certain topologies. This occurs when multiple paths share a common node, creating bottlenecks that reduce throughput and increase overhead. In Figure 1a, router E learns two lowest-cost routes to reach G : $[A, B, C, F, G]$ and $[F, G]$, both passing through node F . This effectively reduces the two options to a single path. Meanwhile, a disjoint but higher-cost route via $[A, B, C, D, \dots, I, H, G]$ is ignored, demonstrating how cost-based decisions can lead to suboptimal forwarding.

A similar issue arises when a router appears in the middle of its own forwarding path. In Figure 1b, router C has three paths to reach D : a direct link, one via B , and another via F . Node B routes to D via $[A, E, F, C, D]$, and F uses $[E, A, B, C, D]$. After cost updates, C sees a direct path of cost 1, and two cost-6 routes that loop through itself, relying again on $C - D$. However, a more efficient option $[F, G, H, \dots, L, D]$, that avoids the loop and dependency on $C - D$, is not included in the solution due to its cost 8. This would give C two independent routes: one with cost 1 and another with cost 8, improving robustness and throughput.

A. Path Vector

One approach to mitigate routing loops is path control using a vector of node names, taking advantage of NDN’s use of named prefixes. In this method, which we call PathVector,

Figure 2. Message size comparison (in bytes).

each route advertisement includes the nodes along the path, with each router appending its own name to the path vector. Upon receiving a vector, a router checks for its own name to detect potential loops and may discard the route if a loop is identified. While effective, this method introduces overhead due to the increasing length of name vectors, leading to larger message sizes.

To evaluate this approach, we implemented PathVector using the NDN Distance Vector Routing protocol (NDVR) [8]. In this implementation, a name vector is added to the prefix advertisement message, DVINFO. However, scalability issues arise as message size increases – from a few hundred bytes in NDVR to several thousand bytes in PathVector. This significant growth, shown in Figure 2, highlights the need for a more scalable solution.

B. Harnessing probabilistic data structures

Our solution utilizes a variation of the original Bloom Filter, the Invertible Bloom Filter (IBF) [9], offering advantages like probabilistic counting, safe removal, and filter comparison. The IBF maps input data to a small number of bits, which are stored at specific array positions. These positions are later checked to determine if an element might belong to the set.

Table I
DVINFO MESSAGE MODEL WITH IBF.

Prefix	NumSeq	Orig	NextHops
/ndn/d-site	x	/d	[0110000000000100000000000001]
			[01100000000000010000000000011]
			[01100000000000100000000000110]
			[0000100100100000000000001011]
			[01100000000000100000000000011]

The mechanism guarantees no false negatives and allows a controllable rate of false positives.

The probability of false positives p can be minimized by solving the Equation 1 [6], where k is the number of hash functions, m is the bit array size, and n is the number of inserted elements (cardinality). As $k \cdot \frac{n}{m}$ increases, the false positive rate rises; conversely, reducing this ratio lowers it. For the network topology in Figure 1b with 12 nodes, we used $k = 3$, $m = 64$, and $n = 12$, resulting in a false positive rate of approximately $p = 0.0796$ (7.96%). In this experiment, no route losses due to false positives were observed.

$$p = (1 - e^{-\frac{k \cdot n}{m}})^k \quad (1)$$

1) *Prefix Broadcasting Message Using Invertible Bloom Filter (IBF)*: In our DVINFO use case, we replace the explicit list of node names in route announcements with an Invertible Bloom Filter (IBF). During route dissemination, each router inserts its identifier into the filter. Upon receiving a route announcement, a router checks if its identifier is in the IBF. If present, the route is discarded to avoid loops or redundant paths. Additional heuristics can be developed to further eliminate suboptimal routes. The main advantage of this approach is its compactness: instead of storing full router names, which may consume hundreds of bytes, each path is represented using only 64 bits, as shown in Table I. Figure 2 illustrates the significant reduction in message size when using this probabilistic structure compared to the *PathVector* approach.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

All experiments were conducted on an Ubuntu 20.04 LTS system with an Intel i5 3.2 GHz CPU and 12 GB of RAM, using the MiniNDN 0.5.0 emulator [8]. Each scenario was replicated 10 times to ensure statistical reliability. The experiments were divided into two parts: the first compares the original NDVR with the NDVR using the solution based on the Invertible Bloom Filter. The RANDOM forwarding strategy, as described in [10], was used. After routing convergence, consumer nodes issued Interest packets across the topology. The experiment lasts 360 seconds. In the second, the NDVR based on the Invertible Bloom Filter is compared with NLSR. The scenario using the real NDN testbed topology is being used. The experiment lasts 360 seconds. It begins with the convergence of the protocols, followed by a period of stability. From that point on, all nodes start sending Interests to each other, and the most connected node is shut down for 60 seconds, leading to protocol reconvergence. After this time, the node most connected is turned on again and the protocol is still seeking convergence.

A. First Experiment - NDVR vs NDVR IBF-based

Experiments using the topology in Figure 1b were conducted with router C as the consumer and router D as the producer. Without the IBF mechanism, three routes were established: the direct $[C, D]$ route, a path via node B $[B, A, E, F, C, D]$, and one via node F $[F, E, A, B, C, D]$. However, both indirect routes ultimately rely on the $C - D$ link, causing a bottleneck and reducing the network to a single usable path. This resulted in high rate of unsatisfied Interests due to the forwarding loops.

With the IBF-enhanced implementation, optimized routing paths were established, such as disjoint paths $[C, D]$ and $[F, G, H, \dots, L, D]$, allowing for bandwidth aggregation across independent links. This significantly improved Interest satisfaction rates, as shown in Figure 3, as a result of reduced looped Interests. These results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed approach in optimizing routes and enhancing performance.

Figure 3. Satisfied vs. Unsatisfied interests.

B. Second Experiment - NDVR IBF-based vs NLSR

In this second experiment, using the real NDN testbed topology, the Bloom Filter-based NDVR was compared with the NLSR protocol. It consists of 38 nodes distributed around the world, creating some loop situations.

The results show that the solution provides an advantage in reducing the delay in recovering forwarded Interests and achieves a higher number of satisfied Interests when using the Invertible Bloom Filter-based solution, as can be seen in Figure 4 and Figure 5. Moreover, we observed lower CPU and RAM usage overhead in Figure 6. The NDN testbed topology is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 4. Satisfied Interests NDVR+IBF vs NLSR.

Figure 5. Latency NDVR+IBF vs NLSR.

Figure 6. Overhead CPU and RAM Memory.

Figure 7. The tested NDN physical topology.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper demonstrates how probabilistic data structures enhance route optimization by eliminating next hops that cause loops and bottlenecks. Experimental results show that routes established using this approach achieve higher Satisfied Interest rates. Future work will focus on refining the modeling process and integrating it with forwarding strategies to fully leverage the benefits of optimized routes.

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REFERENCES

- [1] L. N. Sampaio, A. E. Freitas, I. V. Brito, F. R. C. Araújo, and A. V. Ribeiro, "Revisitando as icns: Mobilidade, segurança e aplicações distribuídas através das redes de dados nomeados," *Sociedade Brasileira de Computação*, 2021.
- [2] L. Wang, A. Lane, C. Serban, J. Elwell, A. Afanasyev, and L. Zhang, "Investigating the Synergy between Routing and Forwarding Strategy in NDN Networks," in *Proceedings of the 10th ACM Conference on ICN*, 2023, pp. 67–77.
- [3] F. A. Karim, A. H. M. Aman, R. Hassan, K. Nisar, and M. Uddin, "Named data networking: A survey on routing strategies," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 90254–90270, 2022.
- [4] A. Marandi, T. Braun, K. Salamatin, and N. Thomos, "Bfr: a bloom filter-based routing approach for information-centric networks," in *2017 IFIP Networking Conference (IFIP Networking) and Workshops*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–9.
- [5] I. V. S. Brito, "NDVR: NDN Distance Vector Routing," Federal University of Bahia, Tech. Rep., 2021.
- [6] B. H. Bloom, "Space/time trade-offs in hash coding with allowable errors," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 13, no. 7, pp. 422–426, 1970.
- [7] V. Patil, S. Theeranantachai, B. Zhang, and L. Zhang, "Poster: Distance vector routing for named data networking," in *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on emerging Networking EXperiments and Technologies*, 2024, pp. 23–24.
- [8] I. V. S. Brito and L. N. Sampaio, "Roteamento em redes de dados nomeados com ndvr: um protocolo leve e eficiente para disseminação de informações de alcançabilidade," in *Anais do XXXIX SBRC 2021*. SBC, 2021, pp. 574–587.
- [9] M. T. Goodrich and M. Mitzenmacher, "Invertible bloom lookup tables," in *2011 49th Annual Allerton Conference on Communication, Control, and Computing (Allerton)*. IEEE, 2011, pp. 792–799.
- [10] C. S. Pratama, M. I. Arrachman, M. S. Nurrasyid, E. A. Z. Hamidi, R. M. Negara, S. Ahdan, R. Mayasari, and N. R. Syambas, "Random load balancing in mini-ndn using modified inherent topology," in *2023 9th International Conference on Wireless and Telematics (ICWT)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6.